

THE CULTURE OF CENTRAL ASIA ON THE EXAMPLE OF UZBEKISTAN.

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Abstract: This article will deal with the vibrant culture of Central Asia by deeper looking at shiny examples of long-standing traditions and customs, which has been existing since ancient times, in the area of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: traditions, customs, culture, residents, historical places, vibrant, unique, inhabit, territory, incorporating, ancient, modern, tribes, painting, cuisine, engraving, enameling, Orient

Introduction

It is clear that every nation has its own established customs and traditions, which have been passing down over centuries and residents of one particular area follow them and live according to their culture. If we have a look closely at the Central Asian culture, it is possible to see some similarities between countries situated in Central Asia and we can be aware of them by discussing the culture of one of the historical places which is called Uzbekistan.

The culture of Uzbekistan is vibrant and unique – It was formed over thousands of years, incorporating the traditions and customs of the peoples who at various times inhabited the territory of modern Uzbekistan. The ancient Persians, Greeks, Arabs, Chinese, Russians, and nomadic Turkic tribes have all contributed to Uzbek culture, which is considered to be epitome of Central Asian, crossroads cultures. The traditions reflecting the multinational nature of Uzbekistan are omnipresent in its music, dance, painting, applied arts, language, cuisine, and clothing. Each region of this country owns its unique shades as well, which are most clearly manifested in national dress and local dialects.

So as to get acquainted with such richness and diversity, one must travel but attending and participating in Uzbek festivals is one of the great chance to be fully informed about whole palette of culture in this country in one place. Because the festivals attract creative souls from all regions of the country, and here that you can see the full assortment of Uzbek dances, music, and applied arts. For instance, one of such interesting festivals is ‘Sharq Taronalari’, which is celebrated in every two years. This festival involves many

representatives who have artistic talent from all of the continent globally and It is also a key of opportunities for watching the cultural performances of different nations.

Music also plays a pivotal role in Uzbek culture. Shashmaqom is a form of classical music similar to classical Persian music.Folk music lives on in religious and family events such as weddings as well as special events.

If It comes to the applied art of Uzbekistan,a wide variety of style,materials and ornamentation obviously spring to our mind.Silk,ceramics and cotton weaving,stone and wood carving ,leather stamping,metal engraving,calligraphy and miniature painting are some genres passed down from ancient times.If we lookback to the history,Uzbekistan was recognized as one of the main central cities in the Great Silk Road so that we can see a lot of bright examples of works of an art,and handcrafting.Even today,Uzbek craftsmen still practice ancient jewellery making techniques for cutting gemstones,grain filigree,granular work,engraving and enameling.

How about wedding traditions? Like many Asian nations,most festive Uzbek customs are related with major family.Traditionally,in Uzbekistan couples get married by other close relatives who act as matchmakers.They firstly gather some information about future bride and visite girl's house.It is only on the third visit that the girl and her family give their consent to be matched.In fact,wedding traditions consist of 10 events such as eating sweets,engagement,drawing henna,father's pilaf,clothe in a robe,evening ceremony,bride seeing,and greeting son-in-law.

We cannot imagine each moment without uzbek traditional meals and when we think about these, the first ideas that come to everyone's mind are uzbek pilaf and bread.Bread holds a special place in Uzbek culture.At mealtime,bread will be spread to cover the entire dusterhon.Traditional uzbek bread ,tandir non, is flat and roun,It is always torn by hand,never placed upside down,and never thrown out.Pilaf is also one of the famous meals in Central Asia and there is no event without cooking uzbek pilaf.

Conclusion

Uzbekistan has one of the brightest and original cultures of the Orient. All of them are based on hospitality,respect,and collectivism.In every peculiarity of the traditions ,from its stunning views of mausoleums and minarets,ending with works of arts and crafts,the long and ancient history of the country is harmonized.Come to Uzbekistan and get acquainted with the culture of our country.

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